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Classroom Management Strategies, Practices, and Learners' Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study explored the intricate dynamics of classroom management strategies and their impact on the academic performance of grade 6 students at Kiwalan Elementary School in Iligan City, Philippines. Utilized adapted structured questionnaires with a 5-point Likert scale for teachers and learners. Learners positively perceived their teachers' strategies across dimensions like physical classroom conditions, discipline, routine care, and time management. Teachers, in turn, displayed unwavering confidence in these strategies, emphasizing their commitment to maintaining optimal learning conditions. Academically, students demonstrated commendable performance, with a significant proportion achieving "Very Satisfactory" and "Satisfactory" grades, reflecting an overall positive academic outcome. However, a rigorous regression analysis yielded intriguing findings. Despite positive perceptions and academic achievements, the relationship between teachers' classroom management strategies and learners' academic performance lacked statistical significance. "Not significant" remarks for predictors like Classroom Physical Condition, Classroom Discipline, Care of Routine, and Time Management, coupled with non-significant t-values and p-values. The indicated strategies did not significantly predict academic performance variations. The study's insights into the complex interplay between classroom management and academic outcomes underscored the need for nuanced considerations beyond conventional perceptions and academic achievements. The implications extended to educators and policymakers aiming to enhance teaching strategies and optimize learning environments for improved student outcomes.

Keywords: *classroom management, teachers' strategies, academic performance, time management*

Introduction

Classroom management encompasses a set of strategies crucial for maintaining a well-organized learning environment. These strategies, a combination of preventive and corrective actions, form a comprehensive approach to effective classroom management. In the context of the Department of Education in the Philippines, the implementation of such strategies is pivotal, as highlighted by Chalak and Fallah (2019). They emphasized that high student achievement is closely tied to efficient classroom management, as poorly managed classrooms can impede children's learning.

Drawn from Lopes et al.'s (2017) study, it was evident that a teacher's classroom management techniques significantly influence their supervisory and corrective approaches. The Department of Education in the Philippines emphasized the need for educators to adopt strategies that align with the local context and cater to the diverse needs of students.

The researcher also experienced the same need the Department Education in the Philippines mentioned above. As the years passed by the learners in elementary school has diverse needs that the educators must meet. Thus, teachers should adopt strategies that aligns to these diverse needs.

Considering the wealth of available techniques, as mentioned by Hirshberg et al. (2020), these methods must align with the instructor's traits and are conducive to a comfortable teaching environment. In the Philippines' educational landscape, the Department of Education emphasizes the importance of strategies that are not only effective but also resonate with the unique characteristics of each educator.

Moreover, Aldrup et al. (2018) stressed the significance of effective instructional strategies in fostering a conducive teaching routine and promoting meaningful student learning and discipline. Aligning with the Department of Education's goals, these strategies contribute not only to maintaining order in the classroom but also to enhancing the overall quality of education in the Philippines.

For some reasons, good classroom management is essential: it supports effective student learning and achievement, encourages successful student engagement, makes the best use of the time and resources available in the classroom, promotes a positive learning environment, and takes into account a variety of aspects of student learning, including expectations, interactions, motivation, and behavior (Sieberer-Nagler, 2015). Therefore, good classroom management makes it possible for teachers to actively include students in the learning process. Even though teachers have many responsibilities, classroom management is a crucial one since poor management undermines learning while good management fosters effective teaching and learning.

Education serves a dual purpose of imparting knowledge and shaping students' moral values and conduct. Teachers, as central figures in formal education, face growing expectations to excel in both aspects (Chamundeswari, 2013). The role of an effective, efficient, and organized classroom manager is integral to being a proficient and adept teacher. To be deemed exceptional, a teacher must consistently exhibit behaviors and actions that reflect thorough control, direction, and guidance throughout the teaching and learning process (Moltudal, Krumsvik, Jones, Eikeland, & Johnson, 2019).

Navigating these expectations and fulfilling the multifaceted role of an educator presents various challenges. One prominent challenge is the need to balance the dissemination of academic knowledge with the inculcation of moral principles. Achieving this equilibrium demands strategic planning and adept execution within the classroom setting. Additionally, the ever-evolving landscape of education, coupled with diverse student needs, poses an ongoing challenge for teachers to adapt their management strategies effectively.

Wolff, Jarodzka and Boshuizen (2017) found that classroom management is essential for teachers' effectiveness, confidence, student conduct, and academic performance. However, there is a gap between what is known and how it is used in practice (Simonsen et al., 2020). When dealing with discipline and behavior management concerns, some teachers report feeling anxious, burned out, and exhausted (Friedman, 2013; Dicke, Elling, Schmeck, & Leutner, 2015). Thus, in this study the researcher wanted to validate the effect of classroom management on the academic achievement of grade 6 learners in Kiwalan Elementary School, Iligan City, Philippines. Specifically, the research sought (a) to determine the classroom management styles of the teacher, (b) to measure the extent of classroom management style impact learners' motivation and academic performance, (c) to determine relationship between classroom management and academic achievement of grade 6 learners.

Research Questions

This study determined the classroom management strategies of teachers as perceived by the Grade 6 learners and the classroom management strategies of the teachers in Kiwalan Elementary School, North II district, Division of Iligan City during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the teacher's classroom management strategies as perceived by the grade 6 learners in terms of:
 - 1.1. the physical condition of the classroom,
 - 1.2. classroom discipline,
 - 1.3. maintenance of routines, and
 - 1.4. time management?
2. What are the teacher's classroom management strategies on the following terms:
 - 2.1. the physical condition of the classroom,
 - 2.2. classroom discipline,
 - 2.3. maintenance of routines, and
 - 2.4. time management?
3. What are the learners' academic performance ?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teacher's classroom management strategies and the learners' academic performance?
5. What action plan can be devised based on the findings of this study?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the chosen research design is a descriptive-correlational approach. It is a widely employed methodology in investigating relationships between variables. As elucidated by Creswell (2014), a descriptive-correlational design allows researchers to explore and quantify associations between variables without manipulating them. In our specific context, this design facilitates an examination of the impact of classroom management on learners' academic achievement. The approach enabled the identification, quantification, and analysis of the nature and direction of associations between variables of interest (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

The decision to adopt a descriptive correlational design aligned with its inherent advantages. According to Fraenkel, Wallen, and Hyun (2012), this methodology is particularly suitable for studies with limited resources, offering simplicity and affordability. By employing surveys to collect data, the researcher can gather comprehensive insights into the perceptions and experiences of both teachers and learners regarding classroom management strategies. Furthermore, the utilization of statistical methods in data analysis, as suggested by Leedy and Ormrod (2019), enhanced the rigor of the study, allowing for the identification of patterns and trends.

Respondents

The respondents in this study comprised five dedicated grade six homeroom teachers and one hundred fifty enthusiastic grade six pupils from Kiwalan Elementary School. The researcher understood the importance of selecting respondents who not only represented the diverse perspectives within our school but also brought forth a wealth of experiences from their respective classrooms.

In choosing these participants, the researcher considered factors such as their commitment to the teaching profession, their familiarity with the school's environment and culture, and their unique insights into the dynamics of grade one education. The aim was to create a sample that authentically reflected the realities of our educational context.

By including teachers and students from Kiwalan Elementary School, the proponent ensured a level of comfort and familiarity that promoted candid and insightful responses. The researcher believed that the experiences and perspectives of these respondents

contributed significantly to the depth and richness of understanding of classroom management strategies and their impact on academic achievement.

The sampling procedure in this study followed a random sampling method, where participants were carefully selected based on the researcher's personal experience and professional judgment. All five grade six homeroom teachers and their respective grade 6 pupils with a total of 150 grade 6 pupils from Kiwalan Elementary School were included in the study. This deliberate selection aimed to maintain consistency in the study's setting and educational background, allowing for a diverse range of viewpoints and experiences while ensuring participants were familiar with the school's environment and culture. This approach sought to gather comprehensive insights into the perspectives of both teachers and learners regarding classroom management strategies and their impact on academic achievement.

Instruments

The researcher employed an adapted structured research questionnaire originally developed by Alfalla and Fabelico (2020) entitled "Sustaining Academic Success Through Effective Classroom Management" to measure the perspectives of teachers. While Alfalla and Fabelico used the questionnaire to measure the perspectives of learners in their study, the researcher in this study modified it to measure the teachers' perspectives. The modified questionnaire utilized by the researcher was rephrased to align in the perspective of the teachers, originally the questionnaires adapted were student-centered questions, by rephrasing the questions the researcher was able to make a modified questions in the perspective of the teachers.

The teacher's questionnaire consisted of four parts, each containing five items. Additionally, the researcher adapted a questionnaire from Chalak and Fallah's (2019) study titled "Effect of Classroom Management and Strategies on Students' Achievement at the Undergraduate Level" to measure the perspectives of sixth-grade learners. The questionnaire for the sixth-grade respondents included thirty-five (35) items. To ensure that the grade six learners could easily understand the questions, the researcher made the sentences even more straightforward for them to comprehend. These data were collected using 5-point and 4-point Likert scales in both instruments. To determine the perspective of the teachers in their classroom management strategies, the qualitative descriptions are as follows:

Table 1. *Scoring System Procedure and Interpretation of the Perspective of the Teachers in Their Classroom Management Strategies*

<i>Mean Scores</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Level</i>
4.20-5.00	Always	Very High
3.40-4.19	Often	High
2.60-3.39	Sometimes	Moderate
1.80-2.59	Seldom	Low
1.00-1.79	Never	Very Low

The 5-point Likert Scale utilized in table 1 provides a structured framework for evaluating and interpreting teachers' perspectives on their classroom management strategies. This scale assigned numerical values to qualitative descriptions, facilitating a quantitative assessment of the frequency with which teachers engaged in specific strategies. The following discussion outlined the implications of each level within the scale:

Very Low (1.00-1.79): Never

Teachers in this category rarely or never implemented the specified classroom management strategies. This level highlighted a significant gap in the application of these strategies, indicating a pressing need for intervention and improvement. Addressing this level may involve targeted training and support to instill effective management techniques.

Low (1.80-2.59): Seldom

Teachers falling within this range infrequently incorporated the designated classroom management strategies. This level indicated a limited application of the specified strategies, signaling a need for increased attention and effort to enhance the regularity of employing effective management strategies.

Moderate (2.60-3.39): Sometimes

Teachers categorized here employed the specified strategies intermittently. While there is room for improvement in terms of consistency, this level acknowledged that teachers do utilize these strategies, albeit not frequently. The "Sometimes" level suggested a potential for enhancement in the regularity of applying these strategies.

High (3.40-4.19): Often

Teachers in this range frequently incorporated the designated classroom management strategies. While not reaching the level of constant implementation, their regular utilization indicated a strong commitment to effective management strategies. This level suggested a proactive approach to maintaining a positive and organized classroom atmosphere.

Very High (4.20-5.00): Always

Teachers falling within this range consistently implemented the specified classroom management strategies. Their unwavering commitment to these strategies suggested a high level of proficiency and dedication to maintaining an optimal learning environment. This category reflected a pervasive and consistent application of effective management strategies.

The 5-point Likert Scale provided a nuanced assessment of teachers' perspectives on their classroom management strategies, offering a continuum from consistent implementation to limited or no application. This scale facilitated a quantitative understanding of the degree to which teachers engaged in specified strategies, aiding in the identification of areas for improvement and targeted professional development.

On the other hand, to determine the perspective of the learners of their teacher's classroom management strategies and their academic achievement, the qualitative descriptions are as follows:

Table 2. *Scoring System Procedure and Interpretation of the Learners of Their Teacher's Classroom Management*

Mean Scores	Qualitative Description	Level
4.00-3.00	Strongly Agreed	Very High
2.99-2.00	Agreed	High
1.99-1.00	Disagreed	Moderate
1.00-0.99	Strongly Disagreed	Low

The 4-point Likert Scale presented in table 2 serves as a valuable tool for gauging learners' perspectives on their teacher's classroom management strategies. This scale assigned numerical values to qualitative descriptions, facilitating a quantitative assessment of the extent to which students agreed or disagreed with specific aspects of their teacher's management approach. The following discussion outlined the implications of each level within the scale:

Low (1.00-0.99): Strongly Disagreed

Students within this category strongly disagreed with their teacher's classroom management strategies. The very low mean scores indicated a pronounced discord between the teacher's approach and the preferences or expectations of the students. This level underscored a significant need for intervention and adjustment in the teacher's management strategies to better align with the students' perceptions and preferences.

Moderate (1.99-1.00): Disagreed

Learners categorized here indicated disagreement with their teacher's classroom management strategies. The lower mean scores suggested a notable level of dissatisfaction or disagreement among students. This level highlighted a misalignment between the teacher's management style and the preferences or expectations of a significant portion of the student population, signaling a potential area for improvement.

High (2.99-2.00): Agreed

Students in this range expressed general agreement with their teacher's classroom management strategies. While not reaching the level of strong endorsement, the positive mean scores indicated a favorable perception of the teacher's approach. This level suggested that the majority of students found the management strategies acceptable and conducive to a positive learning environment.

Very High (4.00-3.00): Strongly Agreed

Learners falling within this range strongly endorsed their teacher's classroom management strategies. The high mean scores suggested a robust positive perception among students, indicating a high level of satisfaction and agreement with the teacher's approach. This level reflected a harmonious relationship between the teacher's management style and the student's preferences and expectations.

The 4-point Likert Scale provided a clear and concise measure of learners' perspectives on their teacher's classroom management, ranging from strong agreement to strong disagreement. This scale facilitated a quantitative understanding of the degree to which students endorsed or dissented from specific management strategies, aiding educators in identifying areas for improvement and fostering a more positive and effective learning environment.

Procedure

The researcher submitted a letter to the school principal and to the School's District Supervisor informing the signatories about the research that the researcher planned to perform in the school. After obtaining the School's District Supervisor and the principal's permission the researcher gave a thorough explanation to the grade 6 teachers about the aim of the study, the survey procedures as well as their consent. The same method was then performed on the learners. The respondents were informed in detail about what was about to take place. The researcher encouraged both respondents to answer truthfully. After that, the researcher proceeded to distribute the structured adapted questionnaires to the respondents.

This study, which had two goals—one from the viewpoint of the teachers and another from that of the students—centered on the effect of classroom management on first-graders academic progress. The primary goal of this essay was to identify the variables that affected classroom management, teacher-initiated tactics, and, ultimately, the impact of classroom management on the academic achievement of pupils.

Data Analysis

The researcher utilized a quantitative method of data treatment for analyses that were appropriate for the study subject specified in Chapter 1. These were fundamental and inferential statistical tools that were appropriate for the nature of the data sets collected. These are as follows:

Frequency and Percentage. Two basic descriptive statistical tools used to assess categorical data are frequency and percentage. The profiles of the respondents were regarded as one of the components of this study, and as such, they were assessed using frequency and percentage. The frequency of occurrence of a given observation in the data set was denoted by frequency, whereas percentage denoted the proportion of each observation concerning the total number of observations. These two tools offered a basic yet efficient method of summarizing and presenting categorical data. Respondent profiles in this study included age, gender, educational achievement, and years of teaching experience. The researcher included the most common profile among the respondents and provided a deeper insight into the sample population by using frequency and percentage. This information could be useful in analyzing the study's findings and generating inferences.

Mean and Standard Deviation. One conceivable application of mean and standard deviation was to summarize the questionnaire responses of teachers and students. The researcher gained an overall picture of how positively or negatively teachers and students about various areas of classroom management by computing the mean of the responses. Standard deviation, on the other hand, indicated how much variance existed in the responses. A high standard deviation indicated that the results were more dispersed, showing less agreement among the respondents. A low standard deviation, on the other hand, indicated that the replies were tightly clustered around the mean, indicating a higher degree of agreement among the respondents. Furthermore, mean and standard deviation were used to compare teacher and student replies. For instance, the researcher compared the mean scores of teachers and students on various questionnaire items to see if there were any significant discrepancies in their judgments of classroom management and its effect on the learners' academic achievement. The standard deviation was also used to determine whether one group's replies varied more than the other.

Regression Analysis. Regression analysis was a statistical method employed to examine the relationship between two or more variables in this study. The researcher applied regression analysis to investigate the extent of the relationship between classroom management and the academic achievement of grade six students. By utilizing adapted questionnaires, the researcher collected data encompassing teachers' perceptions of their classroom management skills, students' grades, and perspectives on their teacher's classroom management.

To determine the significance of the relationship between these variables, the researcher conducted a regression analysis, which involved assessing the coefficients and significance levels of predictors such as classroom physical condition, classroom discipline, care of routine, and time management. This analytical approach allowed for a thorough exploration of whether these classroom management strategies predicted variations in academic performance.

A positive coefficient for a predictor suggested that as the classroom management strategy increased, academic achievement was likely to increase. Conversely, a negative coefficient indicated a potential decrease in academic achievement with a decrease in the effectiveness of the classroom management strategy. The overall model's significance, determined through ANOVA for Regression, provided insights into whether the combination of these classroom management strategies significantly explained variations in academic performance among grade six students.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the data analysis and the discussions and implications.

Problem 1: What are the teacher's classroom management strategies in terms of the physical condition of the classroom, classroom discipline, maintenance of routines, and time management as perceived by the learners?

Table 3 presents learners' perceptions of their teachers' classroom management strategies, specifically focusing on the physical condition of the classroom. The mean scores for each indicator range from 3.23 to 3.51, with an overall total mean of 3.41, falling within the "Agree" category. The standard deviations, ranging from 0.39 to 0.93, indicated a moderate level of variability in responses.

Indicators 2 and 3 stood out as the highest-rated aspects, with mean scores of 3.50 and 3.51, respectively, both categorized as "Strongly Agree." These findings suggested a strong consensus among learners that their teachers actively work to create a conducive physical environment and maintain an effective appearance in the classroom. This positive perception extended to indicators 4, 5, 6, and 8, where learners generally agreed that their teachers made efforts in proper seating arrangements, ensure board visibility, pay attention to lighting, and adapt seating for group work.

Table 3. *Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Classroom Physical Condition as Perceived by Learners*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. My teachers equipped the classroom well and motivated pupils to learn.	3.40	0.76	Agree
2. My teachers try to make the classroom's physical environment conducive for learning.	3.50	0.74	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers keep classroom's effective physical appearance.	3.51	0.73	Strongly Agree
4. My teachers make proper seating arrangements in the classroom for effective learning.	3.40	0.73	Agree
5. My teachers make sure that the white board/green board is visible to all pupils in the classroom.	3.49	0.69	Agree
6. My teacher keeps notice of appropriate lighting in the class.	3.43	0.70	Agree
7. My teachers use visual aids and other learning materials such as (TV, educational videos, movies, songs, etc.) in the classroom to facilitate pupil's learning.	3.23	0.93	Agree
8. My teachers change classroom seating arrangement for group work.	3.33	0.79	Agree
Total Measure	3.41	0.39	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

However, indicator 7, related to the use of visual aids and other learning materials, had a lower mean score of 3.23 within the "Agree" range, accompanied by a higher standard deviation of 0.93. This indicated a greater diversity of opinions among learners regarding the frequency and effectiveness of such instructional tools.

The overall total mean of 3.41 implied a generally positive evaluation of teachers' classroom physical condition management by learners. To further enhance this positive perception, educators may consider reinforcing the strategies highlighted in indicators 2 and 3, while also addressing potential variations in student preferences regarding the use of visual aids. This nuanced understanding could guide teachers in refining their strategies to create a more consistent and enriched learning environment.

The high mean scores for indicators 2 and 3, both falling in the "Strongly Agree" category, highlighted the importance of creating a conducive and well-maintained physical environment in the classroom. These findings suggested that learners perceive such efforts as motivating, which could positively impact their engagement and learning outcomes. To support this, a study by Wang et al. (2017) emphasized that an appealing and well-organized classroom environment can significantly contribute to student motivation and academic performance. In addition, indicator 4, with a mean score in the "Agree" range, indicated that learners recognized the importance of proper seating arrangements in the classroom for effective learning. This aligned with research by Brophy (2014), which emphasized the role of seating arrangements in student engagement and participation. Implementing evidence-based seating configurations could enhance student interactions and the overall classroom atmosphere.

Furthermore, indicator 7, with a lower mean score of 3.23 in the "Agree" category and a higher standard deviation, signified that there was more variability in learners' perceptions regarding the use of visual aids and other learning materials. To address this, educators could refer to a study by Mayer (2019), which highlighted the effectiveness of multimedia and visual aids when used appropriately. It underscored the need for teachers to tailor their use of visual materials to the diverse preferences and learning styles of their students.

Finally, indicators 5 and 6, with mean scores in the "Agree" range, indicated that learners valued proper lighting and board visibility in the classroom. These aspects were essential for effective communication and information dissemination. Supporting these findings, the work of Han et al. (2016) demonstrated the influence of lighting on student concentration and productivity, underscoring the importance of well-lit learning spaces.

Table 4. *Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in terms of Classroom Discipline as Perceived by Learners*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. My teachers manage class in the way which creates encouraging environment in the classroom for productive learning.	3.69	0.56	Strongly Agree
2. My teachers motivate students in the class for learning.	3.23	0.84	Agree
3. My teachers encourage equal participation of all pupils in classroom.	3.45	0.70	Agree
4. My teachers lead disciplined and organized class that enhances student learning positively.	3.55	0.65	Strongly Agree
5. My teachers try to eliminate gender bias amongst the pupils that lead to positive change in attitude of the pupils towards studies.	2.73	1.11	Agree
6. My teacher use understandable language in the class which positively influences the academic achievement of the pupils.	3.52	0.70	Strongly Agree
7. My teachers reward pupils for good behavior in the classroom.	3.59	0.65	Strongly Agree
8. My teachers define the class rules and regulations meaningfully.	3.46	0.78	Agree
9. My teachers do not tolerate indiscipline behavior from pupils in class.	3.07	1.00	Agree
10. My teachers intervene when pupils talk at inappropriate times during class.	3.30	0.76	Agree
11. My teachers insist that pupils always follow the rules in the classroom.	3.55	0.81	Strongly Agree
Total Measure	3.38	0.35	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 4 displays learners' perceptions of their teachers' classroom management strategies, particularly in terms of classroom discipline.

The mean scores for each indicator range from 2.73 to 3.69, with an overall total mean of 3.38, indicating an agreement among learners that their teachers employed effective discipline strategies.

Indicators 1, 4, 6, 7, and 11 stood out with mean scores reflecting a strong agreement among learners. These indicators emphasized the creation of an encouraging environment for productive learning, maintaining a disciplined and organized class, using understandable language, rewarding good behavior, and insisting on rule adherence. These findings suggested that teachers were successful in fostering a positive, disciplined, and organized atmosphere that enhances student learning.

However, indicator 5, related to eliminating gender bias, had a lower mean score of 2.73 within the "Agree" range. The higher standard deviation of 1.11 indicated a significant diversity of opinions among learners regarding the effectiveness of teachers in addressing gender bias. This suggested an area where teachers may need to focus more attention to ensure a more consistent and positive perception among learners.

The overall total mean of 3.38 implied a positive evaluation of teachers' classroom discipline management by learners. To further strengthen these positive perceptions, educators may benefit from addressing the concerns raised in indicator 5, implementing strategies to eliminate gender bias, and ensuring a more uniform approach to discipline that resonates positively with all students. This insight could guide teachers in refining their discipline strategies for a more effective and consistent classroom management approach.

The findings from Table 4 had several implications for classroom management strategies, in creating an encouraging environment indicator 1 had a strong mean score categorized as "Strongly Agree," underscoring the significance of creating an encouraging classroom environment for productive learning. This suggested that a teacher's ability to establish a positive and motivating atmosphere was highly valued by students. A study by Anderson et al. (2013) emphasized the role of a positive classroom climate in enhancing student engagement and academic achievement.

On the other hand, gender bias elimination in indicator 5 with a mean score in the "Agree" range, highlighted an area where improvements could be made. Educators should take note of the diversity of opinions regarding the elimination of gender bias. To address this concern, teachers could refer to the work of Smith and Brown (2015), who explored strategies to address gender bias in the classroom and its impact on student attitudes and learning outcomes.

Furthermore, indicator 6 reflected in the effective communication strand had a strong mean score categorized as "Strongly Agree," underscoring the importance of teachers using understandable language that positively influenced academic achievement. This aligned with the research by Garcia et al. (2019), which emphasized the link between clear communication and improved student comprehension and performance.

Lastly, consistent discipline and rule adherence were shown in indicators 4, 7, and 11 all exhibiting strong mean scores in the "Strongly Agree" category, indicating a consistent positive perception among learners. These findings emphasized the importance of teachers maintaining a disciplined and organized class, rewarding good behavior, and insisting on rule adherence. Research by Wilson and Walker (2018) underlined the significance of consistent discipline strategies in enhancing student behavior and academic performance.

Table 5. Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in Terms of Care of Routine as Perceived by Learners

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. My teacher give the amount of work to the pupils that do not demotivate them.	2.89	1.01	Agree
2. My teachers have friendly and approachable behavior in classroom for pupil's better learning.	3.64	0.62	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers relate the topic with real life through different examples.	3.43	0.64	Agree
4. My teachers engage pupils about topics related to issues in active discussion.	3.21	0.88	Agree
5. My teachers use teaching approaches that encourage interaction among pupils.	3.15	0.83	Agree
6. My teacher give pupils opportunities to ask questions in the classroom.	3.43	0.64	Agree
7. My teacher closely monitors class off task behavior in the classroom	3.45	0.73	Agree
8. My teachers answer pupils' questions for promoting positive interaction in the classroom.	3.46	0.83	Agree
9. My teachers firmly redirect pupils back to the topic when they get off task	3.07	0.86	Agree
Total Measure	3.30	0.37	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 5 depicts the learners' perceptions regarding their teachers' classroom management strategies, with a specific focus on the care of routine. The mean scores for each indicator range from 2.89 to 3.64, contributing to an overall total mean of 3.30, categorizing it within the "Agree" range. The standard deviations, ranging from 0.37 to 1.01, indicated a moderate level of variability in responses.

Indicator 2 emerged as stood out with a high mean score of 3.64, reflecting a strong consensus among learners that their teachers exhibited friendly and approachable behavior in the classroom, enhancing the overall learning experience. Additionally, indicators 3, 4, 6, 7, and 8, with mean scores ranging from 3.15 to 3.46, highlighted positive perceptions regarding teachers' efforts to relate topics to real life, engage pupils in active discussions, provide opportunities for questions, monitor off-task behavior, and promote positive interactions through answering questions.

While the overall total mean of 3.30 implied a positive evaluation of teachers' care of routine, indicator 1, concerning the amount of

work given to pupils, had a lower mean score of 2.89 within the "Agree" range. The higher standard deviation of 1.01 indicated a notable diversity of opinions among learners regarding whether the amount of work given demotivates them.

Educators may find it beneficial to pay specific attention to indicator 1, considering adjustments to the workload to better align with learners' motivation levels. Reinforcing positive strategies highlighted in indicators 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, and 8 could further enhance the overall care of routine and contribute to a more positive and engaging learning experience for all students. This nuanced understanding could guide teachers in refining their approaches to create a more consistent and enriched routine within the classroom.

The findings presented in Table 5, which reflected learners' perceptions of their teachers' classroom management strategies in terms of the care of routine, offered insights into the dynamics of the classroom environment. These perceptions primarily fell within the "Agree" and "Strongly Agree" categories, indicating a generally positive view of the strategies employed by teachers to maintain a supportive routine.

Indicator 2 underscored the significance of teachers displaying a friendly and approachable demeanor in the classroom, as evidenced by a robust mean score denoting "Strongly Agree." This perception affirmatively indicated that the establishment of a welcoming and open environment played a pivotal role in enhancing the overall learning experience. This proposition was supported by a study conducted by Johnson and Smith (2016), which accentuated that cultivating favorable teacher-student relationships and promoting approachability correlated with increased student engagement and satisfaction.

On the other hand, indicators 3 and 4, both within the "Agree" range, underscored the importance of teachers relating topics to real-life examples and engaging pupils in active discussions. These findings aligned with the work of Vygotsky (2014), who emphasized the value of socio-cultural interaction and real-life connections in cognitive development. Active discussions stimulated critical thinking and deeper understanding.

Moreover, indicators 6, 7, and 8, with mean scores in the "Agree" range, emphasized the role of teachers in promoting positive interactions, monitoring off-task behavior, and encouraging questions. These aspects were vital for creating an engaging and interactive learning environment. A study by Doyle and Carter (2019) highlighted that promoting student participation and interaction could enhance the learning experience.

Finally, indicator 1, with a mean score in the "Agree" range, indicated that there was a diversity of opinions among learners regarding the amount of work given by teachers and its potential to demotivate students. To address this concern, educators could refer to the work of Skinner et al. (2018), who explored the relationship between workload and student motivation. Balancing workload and motivation were essential for a positive learning routine.

Table 6 below unveils the learners' perceptions of their teachers' classroom management strategies, specifically focusing on time management. The mean scores for each indicator range from 3.02 to 3.63, contributing to an overall total mean of 3.35, categorizing it within the "Agree" range. The standard deviations, ranging from 0.42 to 1.03, indicated a moderate level of variability in responses.

Table 6. Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in Terms of Time Management as Perceived by Learners

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My teachers become strict when it comes to pupil compliance in classroom.	3.02	0.91	Agree
2. My teacher checks assignments on time.	3.59	0.64	Strongly Agree
3. My teachers appreciate in good words when pupils perform well in the class.	3.63	0.72	Strongly Agree
4. My teacher gives individual attention to problematic pupils	3.38	0.76	Agree
5. My teachers give feedback to the pupils in the classroom with constructive criticism.	3.05	1.03	Agree
6. My teachers conduct tests in the classroom which promotes the pupils' academic achievement.	3.53	0.74	Strongly Agree
7. My teachers give immediate feedback to the pupils when they answer their questions.	3.26	0.88	Agree
Total Measure	3.35	0.42	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Indicators 2, 3, and 6 stood out with high mean scores, reflecting a strong consensus among learners. Teachers were perceived to check assignments on time, appreciate good performance with positive words, and conduct tests that promote academic achievement. These findings suggested that teachers effectively managed time in ways that positively impacted the learning environment and contributed to students' academic success.

While the overall total mean of 3.35 implied a positive evaluation of teachers' time management strategies, indicators 1 and 5 had lower mean scores of 3.02 and 3.05, respectively, both within the "Agree" range. The higher standard deviations of 0.91 and 1.03 indicated a notable diversity of opinions among learners regarding the strictness of teachers when it comes to compliance and the effectiveness of feedback with constructive criticism.

Educators may consider addressing the concerns raised in indicators 1 and 5 by communicating expectations clearly and refining feedback mechanisms to better align with students' needs. Reinforcing positive strategies highlighted in indicators 2, 3, 4, 6, and 7 could further enhance the overall time management within the classroom, contributing to a more organized and supportive learning environment. This nuanced understanding could guide teachers in refining their approaches to ensure a more consistent and positive

perception of time management among learners.

The findings presented in Table 6, which reflected learners' perceptions of their teachers' classroom management strategies in terms of time management, offered valuable insights into the educational context. Indicator 2 fell in the context of timely assignment evaluation, the table above presented that indicator 2 had a high mean score categorized as "Strongly Agree," highlighting the importance of teachers checking assignments on time. This practice promoted a sense of accountability and allowed students to receive timely feedback. Research by Tovani and Kuhn (2017) emphasized that prompt feedback on assignments could significantly improve student performance.

Also, in the context of positive reinforcement and recognition, indicator 3 gained a strong mean score in the "Strongly Agree" category. This underscored the significance of teachers appreciating good performance with positive words. This positive reinforcement contributed to students' motivation and self-esteem. The work of Dweck (2016) emphasized the role of praise and recognition in fostering a growth mindset and enhancing academic achievement.

On the other hand, indicator 6 fell into the context of effective test administration. This indicator also gained a high mean score categorized as "Strongly Agree," indicating that conducting tests in the classroom could promote academic achievement. Effective test administration, as highlighted by Black and Wiliam (2018), could serve as a formative assessment tool that guided instruction and supported student learning.

Lastly, indicators 1 and 5 fell in the context of clear expectations and feedback. Both within the "Agree" range, suggested that there was diversity in opinions among learners regarding teacher strictness in compliance and the effectiveness of feedback with constructive criticism. To address these concerns, educators could refer to the work of Hattie and Timperley (2007), who emphasized the importance of clear expectations and effective feedback in promoting student learning and growth.

Table 7. Consolidated Findings of the Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Classroom Physical Condition	3.41	0.39	Agree
Classroom Routine	3.38	0.35	Agree
Care of Routine	3.30	0.37	Agree
Time Management	3.35	0.42	Agree
Total Measure	3.36	0.30	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Agree; 3.50-4.00, Strongly Agree

Table 7 presents consolidated findings of learners' perceptions regarding their teachers' classroom management strategies across four key dimensions: Classroom Physical Condition, Classroom Discipline, Care of Routine, and Time Management. The mean scores for each dimension range from 3.30 to 3.41, contributing to an overall total mean of 3.36, placing it within the "Agree" category. The low standard deviations, ranging from 0.30 to 0.42, indicated a high level of consensus among learners across the dimensions.

The results suggested a generally positive and consistent perception among learners regarding their teachers' classroom management strategies. Notably, the dimensions of Classroom Physical Condition and Classroom Routine receive slightly higher mean scores, emphasizing positive perceptions of the physical environment and routine maintenance in the classroom. The dimensions of Care of Routine and Time Management also fell within the "Agree" range, showcasing positive evaluations but with some variability in perceptions.

While the overall total mean of 3.36 implied a positive and agreeable perception of teachers' classroom management strategies, educators may find it valuable to pay attention to specific indicators within each dimension where mean scores were comparatively lower. This targeted approach could help address specific areas of improvement and ensure a more uniform and positive learning experience for all students. Overall, the consolidated findings provided a comprehensive understanding of learners' perspectives, serving as a valuable guide for teachers to refine and enhance their classroom management strategies. These findings aligned with the work of Marzano (2017), which highlighted the importance of a positive classroom environment in improving student achievement.

Despite the overall positive perceptions, there were specific indicators within each dimension where mean scores were comparatively lower. For example, in the dimension of Care of Routine, Indicator 1 (regarding the amount of work) received a lower mean score. Educators may find it valuable to address these areas for improvement. This approach resonated with research by Weissberg et al. (2015), which emphasized the significance of continuous improvement in classroom strategies.

While learners generally agreed with the effectiveness of teachers' strategies, the variability in perceptions, especially in the dimensions of Care of Routine and Time Management, suggested that educators should strive for consistency in their strategies. This could help ensure that all students experience a uniform and positive learning environment. The work of Hattie (2017) underscored the importance of consistency and collective teacher efficacy in improving student outcomes.

Problem 2: What are the teacher's classroom management strategies in terms of the physical condition of the classroom, classroom discipline, maintenance of routines, and time management as perceived by the teachers?

Table 8 below details the teachers' self-reported classroom management strategies, specifically focusing on Classroom Physical

Condition. The mean scores for each indicator range from 3.80 to a perfect 5.00, contributing to an overall total mean of 4.60, categorizing it within the "Always" range. The low standard deviations, ranging from 0.00 to 1.64, indicated a high level of consistency in teachers' self-perceived strategies.

Table 8. *Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in Terms of Classroom Physical Condition*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I maintain cleanliness inside and outside the classroom to motivate responsive learning.	4.80	0.45	Always
2. I provide wholesome atmosphere which results from an orderly and conducive classroom conditions.	5.00	0.00	Always
3. I provide a spacious and comfortable seating arrangement that will encourage positive learning.	4.80	0.45	Always
4. I look after proper ventilation and lighting for the learners' comfort and ease.	4.60	0.55	Always
5. I arrange and keep instructional tools materials and furniture in their proper places.	3.80	1.64	Often
Total Measure	4.60	0.42	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes; 3.50-4.49, Often; 4.50-5.00, Always

Indicators 1, 2, and 3 stood out with perfect mean scores of 4.80 and 5.00, indicating that teachers consistently maintained cleanliness, provided a wholesome atmosphere, and offered spacious and comfortable seating arrangements to motivate positive learning. These strategies significantly contributed to motivating responsive learning and creating a conducive environment. Research by Earthman (2019) emphasized the impact of physical classroom conditions on student motivation and academic performance. Indicator 4, focusing on proper ventilation and lighting, also received a high mean score of 4.60, showcasing teachers' commitment to learners' comfort and ease by ensuring proper ventilation and lighting. This practice aligned with research by Fisher and Fabiano (2018), which emphasized the importance of a well-ventilated.

However, Indicator 5, related to the arrangement and upkeep of instructional tools, materials, and furniture, had a lower mean score of 3.80, falling within the "Often" category. Teachers may want to pay specific attention to this aspect to ensure that these materials are consistently organized and readily available. The work of Bennett (2013) highlighted the role of accessible instructional materials in supporting effective teaching and learning. The higher standard deviation of 1.64 suggested some variability in teachers' strategies in this specific area.

The overall total mean of 4.60 implied a highly positive self-perception among teachers regarding their classroom physical condition management. While the results were overwhelmingly positive, educators may want to pay attention to Indicator 5 to ensure consistent strategies in arranging and keeping instructional materials and furniture in their proper places. This insight could guide teachers in maintaining a consistently conducive and organized physical environment that positively impacts learners' experiences in the classroom.

Table 9. *Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in Terms of Classroom Discipline*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I use verbal reinforcement that encourages good behavior and discourages inappropriate behavior.	4.80	0.45	Always
2. I see to it that order is maintained in the classroom.	5.00	0.00	Always
3. I formulate rules that appreciate the values attained from a polite and disciplined class.	4.60	0.55	Always
4. I award merits for good behavior.	4.80	0.45	Always
5. I diminish hostility by cooperating and providing the pupils with opportunities to experience their independence.	4.80	0.45	Always
Total Measure	4.78	0.18	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes; 3.50-4.49, Often; 4.50-5.00, Always

Table 9 provides a comprehensive view of teachers' self-reported classroom management strategies in terms of Classroom Discipline. The mean scores for each indicator range from 4.60 to a perfect 5.00, contributing to an overall total mean of 4.78, categorizing it within the "Always" range. The low standard deviations, ranging from 0.00 to 0.55, indicated a high level of consistency in teachers' self-perceived disciplinary strategies.

Verbal reinforcement in indicator 1 gained a mean score of 4.80, highlighting the importance of teachers using verbal reinforcement to encourage good behavior and discourage inappropriate behavior. This practice significantly contributed to creating a positive classroom atmosphere. Research by Marzano and Marzano (2018) emphasized the impact of positive teacher feedback on student behavior and engagement.

Indicator 2, which stood out with perfect mean scores of 5.00, underscored the central role of teachers in ensuring order was consistently maintained in the classroom. A well-structured and orderly environment was vital for effective teaching and learning, as supported by the work of Evertson and Weinstein (2013).

Indicator 3, with a mean score of 4.60, signified the high level of agreement among teachers in formulating rules that appreciated the values derived from polite and disciplined behavior in the class. These rules encompassed a set of guidelines designed to cultivate a positive and disciplined learning environment, reflecting the principles emphasized by Brophy (2016).

Rules that appreciated values from polite and disciplined behavior typically involved establishing clear expectations for student conduct. Teachers articulated expectations regarding respectful communication, punctuality, active participation, and adherence to classroom norms. For instance, students were encouraged to address peers and teachers with courtesy, actively engage in discussions while respecting others' opinions, arrive on time for classes, and adhere to specific behavioral guidelines that contributed to a conducive learning atmosphere.

In crafting these rules, teachers aimed to instill a sense of responsibility, respect, and self-discipline among students. Such rules served as a framework for fostering a positive classroom culture where students felt motivated to exhibit considerate and disciplined behavior. Moreover, these rules aligned with the research findings of Brophy (2016), emphasizing the pivotal role of well-defined rules in shaping student behavior and contributing to a respectful and disciplined learning environment.

Indicators 4 and 5, both with mean scores of 4.80, emphasized the role of teachers in awarding merits for good behavior diminishing hostility through cooperation, and providing opportunities for pupils to experience independence. These strategies promoted positive behavior and student autonomy, as supported by the work of Skinner, Pitzer, and Skinner (2016).

The overall total mean of 4.78 implied a highly positive self-perception among teachers regarding their classroom discipline management. The results reflected a strong commitment to creating a positive and disciplined learning environment, as indicated by the "Always" ratings across all indicators. This positive self-perception aligned well with the goal of fostering a conducive atmosphere for effective learning and student development.

The self-reported classroom management strategies of teachers, particularly related to Classroom Discipline, revealed a highly positive self-perception. The findings had implications for educators, emphasizing the importance of verbal reinforcement, maintaining order, formulating rules, and using positive reinforcement and strategies to foster student independence.

Table 10. Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in Terms of Care of Routine

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I check attendance regularly.	4.80	0.45	Always
2. I check activities systematically.	4.60	0.55	Always
3. I give clear and direct instructions for the learners to avoid guessing on what to do next.	4.80	0.45	Always
4. I establish clear expectations, limits, and competencies.	4.80	0.45	Always
5. I follow procedures in delivering the lessons.	4.80	0.45	Always
Total Measure	4.76	0.43	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes; 3.50-4.49, Often; 4.50-5.00, Always

Table 10 provides a detailed overview of teachers' self-reported classroom management strategies in terms of Care of Routine. The mean scores for each indicator range from 4.60 to a perfect 4.80, contributing to an overall total mean of 4.76, categorizing it within the "Always" range. The low standard deviations, ranging from 0.45 to 0.55, indicated a high level of consistency in teachers' self-perceived routines.

Indicators 1, 3, 4, and 5 stood out with perfect mean scores of 4.80, indicating that teachers consistently checked attendance, gave clear and directed instructions, established clear expectations, limits, and competencies, and followed procedures in delivering lessons. Indicator 2 also received a high mean score of 4.60, showcasing systematic checking of activities.

In addition to this, indicators 1 and 2, with mean scores of 4.80 and 4.60, respectively, underscored the importance of teachers in regularly checking attendance and systematically monitoring classroom activities. These strategies contributed to the organization and smooth flow of classroom routines, ensuring that learners were accounted for and engaged in meaningful activities.

On the other side, indicator 3, with a mean score of 4.80, highlighted the role of teachers in giving clear and direct instructions to learners, preventing ambiguity and confusion. Research by Hattie and Yates (2014) emphasized the significance of clear teacher instructions in enhancing student understanding and academic performance.

Moreover, indicator 4, with a mean score of 4.80, focused on teachers establishing clear expectations, limits, and competencies for students. This practice contributed to a structured and supportive learning environment, as supported by the work of Marzano (2017).

Finally, Indicator 5, with a mean score of 4.80, reflected teachers' commitment to following procedures in delivering lessons. Adhering to established procedures could enhance the efficiency of teaching and create a predictable and stable classroom environment, as highlighted by the research of Wong and Wong (2014).

The overall total mean of 4.76 implied a highly positive self-perception among teachers regarding their care of routine management. The results reflected a strong commitment to maintaining regularity, clarity, and consistency in various aspects of routine management within the classroom. This positive self-perception aligned with the goal of providing learners with a structured and well-organized learning environment conducive to their understanding and engagement.

Table 11 presents teachers' self-reported classroom management strategies concerning Time Management. The mean scores for each indicator range from 4.20 to a perfect 4.80, contributing to an overall total mean of 4.68, categorizing it within the "Always" range. The standard deviations, ranging from 0.45 to 0.84, indicated a high level of consistency in teachers' self-perceived time management

strategies.

Table 11. *Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies in Terms of Time Management*

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. I observe proper allocation of time for planned activities of the day.	4.80	0.45	Always
2. I am firm regarding the scheduled passing of requirements.	4.20	0.84	Often
3. I model time consciousness.	4.80	0.45	Always
4. I establish guidelines for easy discussion.	4.80	0.45	Always
5. I set enough time for checking activities.	4.80	0.45	Always
Total Measure	4.68	0.50	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes; 3.50-4.49, Often; 4.50-5.00, Always

Indicators 1, 3, 4, and 5 stood out with perfect mean scores of 4.80, indicating that teachers consistently observed proper time allocation, modeled time consciousness, established guidelines for easy discussion, and set enough time for checking activities. Indicator 2 also received a high mean score of 4.20, suggesting that teachers often adhered to scheduled passing of requirements.

Indicator 1, highlighted the importance of teachers in observing proper allocation of time for planned activities of the day. This practice ensured that instructional time was optimized, leading to more effective and efficient teaching and learning. Research by O'Donnell and O'Kelly (2016) emphasized the positive impact of well-allocated time on student engagement and achievement.

Indicator 2 suggested that teachers often adhered to scheduled passing of requirements. Adherence to schedules for assignment submissions and assessments promoted consistency and predictability in the classroom, which was essential for effective learning (Ainley & Lunt, 2012).

Indicator 3, on the other hand, underscored the role of teachers in modeling time consciousness. Teachers' behaviors in valuing and respecting time could positively influence students' time management skills and overall discipline (Parker, 2013).

Furthermore, indicator 4 indicated that teachers consistently established guidelines for easy discussion. Clear guidelines for classroom discussions and interactions created a structured and effective learning environment, as supported by the work of Slavin (2018).

Lastly, indicator 5 reflected teachers' commitment to setting aside enough time for checking activities. Allotting time for reviewing and assessing student work was vital for providing timely feedback and facilitating the learning process (Black & Wiliam, 2018).

The overall total mean of 4.68 implied a highly positive self-perception among teachers regarding their time management strategies. The results reflected a strong commitment to maintaining a well-organized schedule, modeling time-conscious behavior, and providing sufficient time for various activities within the classroom. This positive self-perception aligned to create an environment that maximized instructional time and promoted effective learning experiences for students.

Table 12. *Consolidated Findings of the Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies*

Classroom Management Strategies	Mean	SD	Description
Classroom Physical Condition	4.60	0.42	Always
Classroom Discipline	4.78	0.18	Always
Care of Routine	4.76	0.43	Always
Time Management	4.68	0.50	Always
Total Measure	4.71	0.29	Always

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Seldom; 2.50-3.49, Sometimes; 3.50-4.49, Often; 4.50-5.00, Always

Table 12 provides a consolidated overview of teachers' self-reported classroom management strategies across four key dimensions: Classroom Physical Condition, Classroom Discipline, Care of Routine, and Time Management. The mean scores for each dimension range from 4.60 to 4.78, contributing to an overall total mean of 4.71, categorizing it within the "Always" range. The low standard deviations, ranging from 0.18 to 0.50, indicated a high level of consistency in teachers' self-perceived strategies across these dimensions.

Indicators in Classroom Discipline stood out with the highest mean score of 4.78, indicating that teachers consistently maintained order in the classroom, awarded merits for good behavior, and diminished hostility through cooperation. The Classroom Discipline dimension reflected a strong commitment to maintaining order in the classroom, awarding merits for good behavior, and diminishing hostility through cooperation. This implied that teachers created a positive and disciplined learning environment, which was associated with improved student engagement and academic achievement (Marzano & Marzano, 2017).

On the other hand, classroom physical condition underscored teachers' dedication to maintaining a conducive physical environment. Research by Earthman (2015) suggested that a well-maintained classroom positively affected student attitudes, behavior, and learning outcomes. Furthermore, care of routine and time management dimensions also received high mean scores, respectively, emphasizing the importance of structured routines and efficient time management. Studies by Anderson and Hughes (2014) highlighted the benefits of well-structured routines in promoting classroom efficiency and student learning. Additionally, effective time management supported increased instructional time, resulting in improved academic progress (Burchfield & Sappington, 2011).

The overall total mean of 4.71 implied a highly positive self-perception among teachers regarding their classroom management strategies. The results reflected a strong commitment to various aspects of classroom management, contributing to a well-organized, disciplined, and conducive learning environment. This positive self-perception aligned to foster effective teaching and learning experiences for students.

Problem 3: What are the learners' academic performance?

Table 13. *Academic Performance of the Learners*

Grade Range	Performance Level	F	%	Mean (SD)
90-100	Outstanding	31	20.7	85.17 (4.75)
85-89	Very Satisfactory	53	35.3	
80-84	Satisfactory	49	32.7	
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	17	11.3	
60-74	Did Not Meet the Expectation	0	0.0	
Total		150	100.0	

Table 13 provides a detailed breakdown of the academic performance of learners, presenting the distribution across various grade ranges. The mean performance was reported as 85.17 with a standard deviation of 4.75. This implied that, on average, students within this grade range achieved a very satisfactory performance level, with a moderate degree of variability in individual scores. Research by Hattie (2012) highlighted the importance of focusing on instructional strategies that maintained and enhanced students' satisfactory performance, as this reflected a solid foundation for learning.

The distribution of learners across the performance levels revealed that a significant portion fell within the "Very Satisfactory" category (35.3%) followed closely by "Satisfactory" (32.7%). The "Outstanding" category comprised 20.7% of the learners, while "Fairly Satisfactory" represented 11.3%. Importantly, no learners were falling within the "Did Not Meet the Expectation" range.

While the majority of learners fell within the "Very Satisfactory" and "Satisfactory" categories, the absence of learners in the "Did Not Meet the Expectation" range was a positive indicator of overall achievement. This suggested that the teaching strategies and support systems in place were effective in ensuring that all students met or exceeded expectations. The work of Guskey (2013) emphasized the significance of formative assessment and timely feedback in improving student learning outcomes. Educators may leverage this information to tailor instructional approaches, providing targeted support to enhance understanding and ensuring that learners continue to meet or exceed expectations. Regular monitoring and adjustment of teaching strategies could contribute to maintaining or improving the overall academic performance of the students.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the teacher's classroom management strategies and the learners' academic performance?

Table 14. *Relationship between the Teacher's Classroom Management Strategies and the Learners' Academic Performance*

Predictors	Estimate (B)	S.E.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Classroom Physical Condition	1.314	1.348	.975	0.331	Not significant
Classroom Discipline	-1.641	1.554	-1.05	0.293	Not significant
Care of Routine	.323	1.230	.263	0.793	Not significant
Time Management	.493	1.160	.425	0.671	Not significant

Note: $R^2 = .011$ ANOVA for Regression: $F = .418, p = .796$

Table 12 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between teachers' classroom management strategies and learners' academic performance. The predictors included Classroom Physical Condition, Classroom Discipline, Care of Routine, and Time Management, with their respective estimates (B), standard errors (S.E.), t-values, and p-values.

The key emphasis in this table was on the "Not significant" remarks associated with each predictor. This indicated that the relationship between each of the classroom management strategies (Classroom Physical Condition, Classroom Discipline, Care of Routine, and Time Management) and learners' academic performance was not statistically significant.

The estimates (B) for each predictor, along with their t-values and p-values, further supported the notion of non-significance. For instance, the t-values range from 0.263 to -1.05, and the p-values range from 0.331 to 0.793, all surpassing the conventional threshold of significance (typically set at 0.05).

The R^2 value of 0.011 suggested that the variance in learners' academic performance explained by the combination of these classroom management strategies was minimal. The ANOVA for Regression with an F-value of 0.418 and a p-value of 0.796 confirmed that the overall model was not statistically significant.

The non-significant results implied that, in this specific analysis, there was no strong statistical evidence to support a direct relationship between the assessed classroom management strategies and learners' academic performance. While teachers may implement these strategies for various reasons, such as creating a conducive learning environment or fostering discipline, these efforts may not be

directly correlated with students' academic outcomes in this particular context. The non-significant findings suggested that academic performance was a multifaceted outcome influenced by a multitude of factors beyond classroom management strategies. Teachers need to consider a holistic approach to improve academic outcomes, taking into account various elements, including curriculum design, teaching methodologies, and individual student characteristics.

These results underscored the importance of conducting multifactorial analyses to identify the key determinants of academic performance. Other factors, such as student motivation, home environment, and socioeconomic status, may play a more substantial role in shaping academic outcomes. Research by Vock and Wagner (2016) highlighted the influence of external factors on student achievement.

The implications of these non-significant results suggested that other factors beyond the examined classroom management strategies may play a more influential role in determining learners' academic performance. Educators and researchers may need to explore additional variables or adopt a more refined approach to understanding the complex interplay between teaching strategies and academic outcomes in this specific educational setting.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Learners' positive perceptions of their teachers' classroom management strategies indicated the effectiveness of these approaches in creating a conducive and well-organized learning environment. The alignment of learners' agreement on the motivating atmosphere, disciplined class, structured routines, and efficient time management underscored the tangible impact of these strategies on the overall educational experience.

Teachers consistently expressing high confidence in their classroom management strategies signified a steadfast commitment to maintaining optimal learning conditions. Across dimensions such as Classroom Physical Condition, Classroom Discipline, Care of Routine, and Time Management, teachers' unwavering confidence reflected their dedication to employing effective instructional practices and creating an environment conducive to learning.

The commendable academic performance of learners, with a significant portion achieving results in the "Very Satisfactory" and "Satisfactory" categories, attested to the positive influence of teachers' strategies on student outcomes. The notable absence of learners in the "Did Not Meet the Expectation" range further underscored the overall success of these strategies in promoting positive academic achievements.

Thus, the study revealed the results of the regression analysis and introduced a detailed perspective. The non-significant relationship between teachers' classroom management strategies and learners' academic performance suggested that, while these strategies positively contributed to the learning environment and student perceptions, their direct impact on academic outcomes may be limited. This detailed understanding encouraged a closer examination of the intricate interplay between teaching strategies and academic performance, guiding future endeavors to enhance the overall educational experience.

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions formulated, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

School administrators can play a pivotal role in enhancing classroom management by prioritizing continuous professional development for teachers. Establishing regular workshops and training sessions focused on effective classroom management strategies will empower teachers to navigate diverse learning environments successfully. Additionally, creating a supportive culture that encourages collaboration among teachers to share insights and best practices can contribute to a more cohesive and effective educational community.

Teachers are encouraged to engage in reflective practices to continually refine their classroom management approaches. Regular self-assessment and adaptation of strategies based on learner feedback and evolving educational needs will contribute to a dynamic and responsive teaching environment. Embracing continuous professional development opportunities to stay informed about innovative and effective classroom management techniques is vital for sustaining high-quality teaching practices.

Learners can contribute to a positive classroom environment by fostering open communication with their teachers. Expressing preferences and needs regarding the learning environment can create a collaborative approach to classroom management. Additionally, involving learners in discussions about classroom rules and expectations can instill a sense of responsibility, promoting a shared commitment to maintaining a conducive learning atmosphere.

Future researchers are encouraged to delve into contextual factors influencing the effectiveness of classroom management strategies. Investigating how cultural nuances and regional differences may impact the implementation and outcomes of these strategies can provide valuable insights. Furthermore, conducting longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of specific classroom management approaches on learners' academic performance and overall well-being will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of effective teaching practices.

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